

ENTRUST

ENsuring Secure and Safe CMD Design with Zero TRUST Principles

ENTRUST Newsletter

Issue 1 | July 2023

Dear reader,

On behalf of the whole ENTRUST consortium, I am happy to welcome you to this first project newsletter.

ENTRUST, as a Horizon Europe project funded by the European Commission, is unique in its kind: It will ensure an end-to-end trust management framework and reasoning system adapted to the needs of medical devices that will also strengthen operational assurance & cybersecurity! It brings together 18 beneficiaries & 2 associated partners from 12 EU countries to support a novel remote attestation mechanism & secure the Required Level of Trustworthiness tailored in each device and function, across a three-year period.

Beyond these, ENTRUST is also extremely ambitious with the development of verified trust models, risk assessment processes, secure lifecycle procedures, security policies and technical recommendations for medical devices. For sure, the learnings of the project will strongly impact the path towards first-ever real-time Conformity Certificates to safeguard connected medical devices in Europe... and beyond! Indeed, we aim in ENTRUST at collaborating with health industries worldwide.

ENTRUST us on this secure road,
We are glad that you are with us for this exciting healthy journey!

Lina Giannakandropoulou, PhD
ENTRUST Project Coordinator

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ENTRUST Blog Posts

ENTRUST at a glance: Trust management of medical devices

Explore the unique challenges faced in ensuring trustworthiness and security in the healthcare industry. Discover the potential risks associated with medical device vulnerabilities and the importance of effective trust management practices. Gain valuable insights into cutting-edge solutions and strategies that can enhance the security of medical devices. Stay informed about the latest advancements in trust management and protect patient safety with ENTRUST's expertise in healthcare cybersecurity.

[Learn More](#)

ENTRUST End-To-End Trust Management: Some Challenges And Possible Solutions

The ENTRUST project aims at developing novel end-to-end trust management and remote attestation mechanisms that will ensure the secure, safe, and correct operation of connected medical devices at runtime. Although these primary goals mainly touch on aspects of cybersecurity, under the surface the project is a complex amalgamation of various state-of-the-art technologies and computer science domains that go beyond security. This blog post is a short overview of some of the project challenges with software engineering flavor and provides an outline of possible solutions.

[Learn More](#)

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ENTRUST Latest News

Project Announcement Letter

The ENTRUST Research and Innovation Action, officially started on January 1st, 2023. The project is funded by European Commission under Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement No. 101095634), and spans on the period January 2023 – December 2025.

[Learn More](#)

ENTRUST 1st Plenary Meeting

Get an exclusive glimpse into ENTRUST's 1st Plenary Meeting in Oslo. Discover the highlights and key discussions from this pivotal event, where experts gathered to shape the future of trust management. Stay up-to-date with ENTRUST's collaborative efforts and innovative strategies to enhance trust in digital transactions.

[Learn More](#)

ENTRUST Forms Powerful Alliance for the revision of MDCG 2019-16 Guideline

ENTRUST recently forged a powerful alliance with its sibling projects in Brussels, establishing a working group dedicated to shaping potential recommendations for the MDCG 2019-16 guideline.

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Project Details:

Project number: 101095634

Project Started: January 2023

Duration: 36 months

The project ENTRUST has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101095634